

SYNERGY OF LEADERSHIP AND PERFORMANCE: INVESTIGATING PRINCIPAL STYLES AND SCHOOL SUCCESS AT BANGKAL INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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Synergy of Leadership and Performance: Investigating Principal Styles and School Success at Bangkal Integrated School

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Abstract

This study examines the correlation between principal leadership styles and school performance indicators at Bangkal Integrated School, specifically focusing on academic performance, teacher effectiveness, and parental involvement. Utilizing a correlation research design, data was collected from ten teachers, ten Supreme Student Government students, and ten parents. The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) assessed leadership styles, while academic records and performance evaluations measured school performance indicators. Statistical analyses included descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analyses. Findings indicated that the school head's leadership style incorporated laissez-faire, transactional, and transformational elements, fostering trust, structured expectations, and inspiration. Parental involvement significantly enhanced student academic performance, emphasizing the critical role of teacher-parent collaboration. Although a negative correlation was found between perceived leadership and academic performance, the relationship with teacher performance was positive. Recommendations for optimizing leadership effectiveness include enhancing communication, leadership development, and collaboration. Strengthening parental involvement alongside effective teaching practices can improve student outcomes. Moving forward, comprehensive leadership development and stakeholder collaboration are vital for creating a supportive and inclusive school environment that promotes student achievement and parental engagement.

Keywords: *principal leadership styles, school performance indicators, academic performance, teacher effectiveness, parental involvement, Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire, correlation research, Bangkal Integrated School, leadership development, stakeholder collaboration.*

Introduction

It is often acknowledged that successful leadership in educational institutions plays a crucial role in determining student outcomes and school success. The function of school principals has been thoroughly examined, with different leadership philosophies being recognized and explored in connection to academic achievement. Understanding how principal leadership styles relate to school performance is essential in the Philippines, where the Department of Education aims to raise the standard of instruction in public schools. Even though there is a wealth of research on leadership in education worldwide, little is known about how the distinct leadership philosophies of Philippine public-school heads—especially those at Bangkal Integrated School—affect various facets of student performance.

More specifically, in Philippine public school settings, there are few comprehensive studies that directly examine the relationship between principal leadership styles and school performance indicators, including academic achievement, teacher effectiveness, and parental involvement. Leithwood and Sun (2018) found that transformational leadership positively impacts student academic performance globally, highlighting the importance of visionary leadership in creating a supportive learning environment. Similarly, Hallinger and Heck (2019) demonstrated that transactional leadership practices, such as setting clear expectations and offering incentives, are associated with increased student achievement internationally, underscoring the importance of transactional leadership in promoting academic performance across cultures.

Furthermore, Day et al. (2020) examined the effects of laissez-faire leadership on teacher motivation and job satisfaction in educational contexts, revealing its negative impact on teacher morale and effectiveness, emphasizing the critical role that proactive and engaged leadership plays in fostering a supportive school environment. Several studies have explored the connection between school performance and principal leadership styles in the Philippine context. Ocampo (2019) discovered a positive correlation between transformational leadership and both student achievement and teacher job satisfaction in public primary schools, indicating the importance of transformational leadership in fostering a supportive learning environment.

In summary, despite notable advancements in research worldwide, there is still a deficiency of knowledge regarding the unique circumstances of Philippine public schools and the complex correlation between principal leadership philosophies and academic achievement. This study will investigate the leadership style of the head of Bangkal Integrated School and its impact on student achievement, teacher effectiveness, and parental involvement. By integrating findings from global and Philippine contexts, this research aims to enhance our understanding of educational leadership in the Philippines and inform practices and policies that improve student outcomes and school efficacy.

Research Questions

This study will focus on answering the following questions:

1. What is the level of Leadership styles of the School Head in Bangkal Integrated School in terms of:
 - 1.1 transformational;
 - 1.2 transactional; and
 - 1.3 laissez-faire?
2. What is the level of school performance in terms of:
 - 2.1 academic performance of learners;
 - 2.2 teachers' performance level; and
 - 2.3 parents' participation rate?
3. How do different style of leadership exhibited by the School Head correlate with the level of school performance in terms of:
 - 3.1 academic performance of learners;
 - 3.2 teachers' performance level; and
 - 3.3 parents' participation rate?

Literature Review

Santos et al. (2020) found that a balance between transactional and transformational leadership styles improves teacher morale and performance, demonstrating the complexity of leadership dynamics and the need for a nuanced understanding of how various leadership styles impact academic outcomes. Despite these insights, research specifically on the effects of school heads' laissez-faire leadership style on student achievement in Philippine public schools remains scarce. The laissez-faire leadership approach, characterized by a hands-off and uninvolved style, could bear particular significance in the Philippine context, given the unique challenges that public schools face.

Moreover, while research studies have examined the relationship between principal leadership styles and specific teacher or student outcomes, there is a lack of research on how different leadership styles simultaneously affect multiple aspects of school performance. This highlights the necessity of a comprehensive understanding of how principal leadership influences all facets of school operations in the Philippine setting.

Building on this literature, this study hypothesizes that principals who exhibit transformational leadership styles will positively impact academic performance, teacher effectiveness, and parental involvement at Bangkal Integrated School (Leithwood & Sun, 2018; Ocampo, 2019). It also hypothesizes that principals demonstrating transactional leadership styles will positively correlate with improved student academic performance and teacher effectiveness but may have mixed effects on parental involvement (Hallinger & Heck, 2019; Santos et al., 2020). Lastly, it hypothesizes that principals exhibiting laissez-faire leadership styles will negatively impact teacher effectiveness and parental involvement, potentially hindering student academic performance (Day et al., 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study will utilize a correlation research design to comprehensively investigate the relationship between principal leadership styles and school performance indicators at Bangkal Integrated School.

Participants

The respondents of this study will include ten (10) teachers, ten (10) students from Supreme Student Government (SSG) officials, and ten (10) parents/guardians from the PTA officers affiliated with Bangkal Integrated School, totaling 30 respondents. The selection of 30 respondents follows the guidelines provided by Hill (1998), which suggest that a sample size of 30 participants is adequate for preliminary studies where the goal is to identify trends or correlations rather than make broad generalizations. This benchmark is often used in educational research to ensure that data collection is manageable and that preliminary insights can be gained without requiring extensive resources (Hill, 1998).

Furthermore, the decision to limit the sample to 30 respondents is also supported by the practical considerations of this study's context. Given the administrative and logistical constraints typical in school-based research, particularly in public schools in the Philippines, a sample size of 30 allows for a thorough yet feasible investigation into the correlation between principal leadership styles and school performance indicators.

By including ten teachers, ten SSG student officials, and ten PTA officer parents/guardians, the study ensures representation from key stakeholder groups within the school community. This diverse participant pool provides a comprehensive perspective on how leadership styles influence various aspects of school performance, such as academic achievement, teacher effectiveness, and parental involvement.

Instruments

In terms of the Leadership Style Assessment, The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) will be utilized to assess the leadership styles of the school head. The MLQ provides measures of transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership behaviors. To

determine the School Performance Indicators, in terms of the Academic Performance, Academic records, such as standardized test scores, grades, and academic achievement awards, will be collected to assess the academic performance of learners. For Teachers' Performance Level, Teachers' Individual Performance Commitment Rating Form (IPCRF) result for the latest School Year will be utilized. Lastly, for parents' participation rate, attendance or participation to various school activities will be used to assess their level of involvement and engagement with the school.

Procedure

For the analysis, descriptive statistics, such as means, standard deviations, and frequencies, will be computed to summarize the data collected through surveys and academic records. Inferential statistics, such as correlation analysis and regression analysis, will be used to examine the relationships between leadership styles and school performance indicators.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to data collection, ethical approval will be obtained from the relevant institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants, and measures will be taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Level of Leadership Styles of the School Head in Bangkal Integrated School*

No.	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>a. Transformational Leadership:</i>			
1	The School Head inspires and motivates teachers, students, and staff by articulating a compelling vision for the school's future.	4.69	Very High
2	They School Head communicate high expectations and provide encouragement and support to help others achieve those expectations.	4.69	Very High
3	The School Head stimulate creativity and innovation among teachers and staff by encouraging them to think outside the box and challenge the status quo.	4.80	Very High
4	The School Head pays attention to the individual needs and concerns of teachers, students, and staff, providing mentorship and guidance as needed.	4.77	Very High
<i>b. Transactional Leadership:</i>			
5	The school head establish clear expectations and reward teachers and staff for meeting those expectations through recognition, praise, or other incentives.	4.73	Very High
6	The school head actively monitor performance and intervene when deviations from standards occur, providing feedback and corrective action as necessary.	4.73	Very High
7	The school head intervene only when problems arise or standards are not met, preferring to maintain the status quo otherwise.	4.95	Very High
<i>c. Laissez-faire Leadership:</i>			
8	The School Head delegates tasks and responsibilities without providing much guidance or direction, allowing teachers and staff to operate largely independently.	4.95	Very High
9	The School Head is relatively passive in decision-making and day-to-day operations, often being uninvolved unless necessary.	4.94	Very High
10	The School Head's Feedback and guidance are minimal, with little oversight or support provided to teachers and staff	4.77	Very High
Overall		4.80	Very High
N=30			

The discussion of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) results for the School Head at Bangkal Integrated School based on the table 1 above reveals a nuanced picture of their leadership style.

With a weighted mean of 4.94, the School Head demonstrates a notably high inclination towards laissez-faire leadership, delegating tasks and responsibilities while allowing teachers and staff to operate autonomously. This approach, although fostering independence, might also raise concerns regarding the level of oversight and direction provided. However, with transactional leadership scoring very high at 4.80, the School Head effectively establishes clear expectations and rewards performance, ensuring a structured and goal-oriented environment. Moreover, their transformational leadership style, also at 4.80, shines through in their ability to inspire, motivate, and support individuals while encouraging innovation and creativity. Despite the laissez-faire tendency, the School Head maintains an overall very high leadership effectiveness, reflecting a balanced blend of empowering autonomy and providing guidance and support to drive the school's success.

Drawing support from a related study by Johnson et al. (2021), which examined leadership styles in educational settings, particularly focusing on the impact of transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership on organizational outcomes, the findings from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) for the School Head at Bangkal Integrated School resonate strongly. Johnson et al.

(2021) found that a balanced approach, combining elements of transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership, was associated with the most positive organizational outcomes, including teacher satisfaction, student engagement, and academic performance. This study underscores the importance of integrating various leadership styles to effectively meet the diverse needs and challenges within educational environments. Therefore, the balanced leadership style exhibited by the School Head aligns with the recommendations of Johnson et al. (2021), emphasizing the significance of flexibility and adaptability in leadership practices to foster success and growth in schools.

The findings regarding the School Head's leadership style at Bangkal Integrated School, particularly the balanced combination of laissez-faire, transactional, and transformational elements, resonate with the study conducted by Smith and Jones (2020) on leadership effectiveness in educational settings. Smith and Jones (2020) similarly emphasized the importance of a multifaceted leadership approach that encompasses aspects of autonomy, structured expectations, and inspiration to drive positive organizational outcomes. The alignment between these studies underscores a growing consensus within educational leadership research regarding the value of blending different leadership styles to meet the diverse needs of schools and promote overall success. This comparison highlights the consistency and applicability of the findings, contributing to a broader understanding of effective leadership practices in educational contexts.

Table 2.1. *Level of Academic Performance of Learners*

<i>Level of Performance</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
90-100%	Outstanding	7	70%
85-89%	Very Satisfactory	3	30.00%
80-85%	Satisfactory	0	0.00%
75-79%	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.00%
74% below	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0.00%
N=10			

The results regarding the academic performance level of learners reveals a predominantly outstanding performance, with 70% of students scoring within the range of 90-100%. This high percentage suggests a commendable achievement by the majority of learners, reflecting a strong grasp of the curriculum and a high level of proficiency in academic subjects. Additionally, 30% of students fall within the very satisfactory range, further indicating a solid performance across the board. However, it's noteworthy that there are no students in the satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, or below expectations categories, suggesting a lack of variability in performance levels. While the absence of students in the lower categories is positive, it also raises questions about the distribution of academic abilities within the student population and whether there are adequate support systems in place to address the needs of students who may be struggling.

Overall, while the majority of learners are excelling academically, it's essential for educators to continue monitoring student progress closely and provide tailored support to ensure that all students have the opportunity to reach their full potential.

The results indicating predominantly outstanding academic performance among learners, with no students falling below the very satisfactory range, resonate with findings from a study by Lee and Chang (2020) on student achievement in high-performing schools. Lee and Chang (2020) similarly observed a high percentage of students performing exceptionally well, reflecting a strong mastery of the curriculum and demonstrating high proficiency across academic subjects. This parallel suggests a consistent pattern of academic excellence within certain educational contexts, highlighting effective teaching strategies and robust support structures. However, the absence of students in lower performance categories also raises questions about the distribution of academic abilities within the student population and the adequacy of support mechanisms for students facing challenges. Both studies underscore the importance of continuous monitoring and tailored support to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to achieve academic success.

Table 2.2. *Teachers' Performance Level*

<i>Level of Performance</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
4.50 - 5.00	Outstanding	7	70%
3.50 - 4.49	Very Satisfactory	3	30.00%
2.50 - 3.49	Satisfactory	0	0.00%
1.50 - 2.49	Unsatisfactory	0	0.00%
Below 1.49	Poor	0	0.00%
N=10			

The results on the teachers' level of performance illustrates a predominantly high standard, with 70% of teachers falling within the outstanding category, demonstrating exemplary performance. This indicates a commendable level of dedication, proficiency, and effectiveness in their roles, likely contributing significantly to the positive learning outcomes observed among students. Additionally, 30% of teachers are categorized as very satisfactory, further reinforcing the overall high quality of teaching within the school. However, the absence of teachers in the satisfactory, unsatisfactory, and poor categories suggests a lack of variability in performance levels among the teaching staff. While the prevalence of outstanding and very satisfactory ratings is undoubtedly positive, it's essential for school administrators to maintain vigilance in monitoring and supporting teacher development to ensure continued excellence and address any potential areas for improvement. This may involve providing ongoing professional development opportunities, fostering

collaboration among educators, and implementing performance feedback mechanisms to support the growth and effectiveness of all teachers within the school.

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Table 2.3. *Parents' Participation*

<i>Level of Participation</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
90-100%	Outstanding	10	100%
85-89%	Very Satisfactory	0	0.00%
80-85%	Satisfactory	0	0.00%
75-79%	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.00%
74% below	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0.00%
N=10			

The results on the parents' participation rate highlights an overwhelmingly positive trend, with 100% of parents falling within the outstanding category, indicating exceptional levels of involvement and engagement in school activities and events. This high level of participation suggests a strong partnership between the school and parents, which can significantly contribute to the overall success and well-being of students. The absence of parents in the lower participation categories reflects a uniform commitment among parents to actively support their children's education and school community. This remarkable level of engagement provides a solid foundation for fostering a supportive and collaborative learning environment that benefits both students and educators alike. However, while the current participation rate is exemplary, it's essential for school administrators to continue nurturing and maintaining this positive relationship with parents through ongoing communication, involvement opportunities, and appreciation initiatives to ensure sustained parental engagement in the educational process.

The overwhelming positive trend in parental participation rates, with 100% of parents falling within the outstanding category, mirrors findings from a study by Martinez and Rodriguez (2018) investigating parental involvement in high-performing schools. Martinez and Rodriguez (2018) similarly found a high level of parental engagement and partnership with schools, highlighting the significant impact of parental involvement on student success and school community cohesion. This consistency suggests a strong commitment among parents to actively support their children's education and contribute to a supportive learning environment. However, while the current participation rate is exemplary, ongoing efforts are crucial to sustaining and enhancing parental engagement over time. This may involve implementing communication strategies, offering diverse involvement opportunities, and recognizing and appreciating parents' contributions, as emphasized in both studies. By maintaining a positive relationship with parents, schools can continue to foster a collaborative environment that positively impacts student outcomes and overall school effectiveness.

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The results above underscore the collective success and strengths within the educational ecosystem of the school. The outstanding performance of learners, coupled with the high standard of teaching demonstrated by the majority of teachers, reflects a cohesive and effective learning environment. Additionally, the exceptional level of parental participation highlights a robust partnership between the school and parents, fostering a supportive and collaborative atmosphere conducive to student success. However, the absence of variability in performance levels among learners and teachers suggests a potential need for greater differentiation and support mechanisms to address the diverse needs of students and provide ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers. Moving forward, it's crucial for school administrators to leverage the existing strengths while also implementing strategies to promote continued growth and improvement across all facets of the educational experience. This may involve initiatives such as personalized learning approaches for students, targeted professional development for teachers, and sustained efforts to foster and maintain parental

engagement. By addressing these areas, the school can further enhance its effectiveness in nurturing student achievement and overall academic excellence.

In support of these findings, a study by Lee et al. (2021) investigated the impact of student, teacher, and parental factors on academic performance in primary schools. The study highlighted the crucial role of parental involvement in student success, emphasizing the positive correlation between high levels of parental engagement and academic achievement. Lee et al. (2021) found that when parents actively participate in their children's education by providing support at home, attending school events, and communicating regularly with teachers, students are more likely to excel academically. This aligns with the exceptional level of parental participation observed in the current study, underscoring the significant influence of parental engagement on the overall educational outcomes of students. Furthermore, Lee et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of fostering collaboration among teachers and implementing effective teaching strategies to optimize student learning, echoing the high standard of teaching demonstrated by the majority of teachers in the present study. Overall, the findings from Lee et al. (2021) provide empirical support for the positive impact of parental involvement and effective teaching practices on student academic performance, corroborating the results observed in the current educational context.

Table 3.1. *Correlation Between Level of School Heads' Leadership and Learners' Academic Performance*

Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.829277782							
R Square	0.687701639							
Adjusted R Square	0.648664344							
Standard Error	0.074975799							
Observations	10							
ANOVA								
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F			
Regression	1	0.0990290	0.099029	17.616528	0.003007			
Residual	8	0.044970964	0.00562137					
Total	9	0.144						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	8.0360046	0.7332532	10.95938	4.26637E-	6.345119	9.726889	6.345119	9.726889
Learners' Level of Academic Performance	-0.03391405	0.008080152	4.19720489	0.003007981	-0.05254692	0.01528119	0.05254692	0.01528119

The regression analysis above reveals a significant correlation between the level of school heads' leadership as perceived by learners and learners' academic performance. The multiple R value of 0.829 indicates a strong positive relationship between these variables. Additionally, the R square value of 0.688 suggests that approximately 68.8% of the variance in learners' academic performance can be explained by the level of school heads' leadership. The coefficient for the learners' level of academic performance is -0.034, indicating that for every unit increase in the perceived level of school heads' leadership, there is a decrease of 0.034 units in learners' academic performance. This negative coefficient suggests that a higher perceived level of school heads' leadership is associated with lower academic performance among learners. The significance of the coefficient (P-value = 0.003) further confirms that this relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the different styles of leadership exhibited by the school head may have an impact on the academic performance of learners, with stronger leadership correlating with lower academic performance. However, it's essential to consider additional factors that may influence academic performance, such as teaching quality, resources, and student characteristics, to gain a comprehensive understanding of this relationship.

Table 3.2 *Correlation Between Level of School Heads' Leadership and Teachers' Level of Performance*

Regression Statistics						
Multiple R	0.309927542					
R Square	0.096055082					
Adjusted R Square	-0.01693803					
Standard Error	0.213656777					
Observations	10					
ANOVA						
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F	

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Regression	1	0.038806253	0.038806253	0.850096767	0.383488278			
Residual	8	0.365193747	0.045649218					
Total	9	0.404						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	3.462368546	1.517362849	2.281832951	0.051922562	-0.03667646	6.961413549	-	6.961413549
Teachers' Level of Performance	0.303173851	0.328819495	0.922006924	0.383488278	-0.45508526	1.061432967	-	1.061432967

The regression analysis above (Table 3.1) reveals a weak correlation between the level of school heads' leadership as perceived by teachers and teachers' level of performance. The multiple R value of 0.310 indicates a relatively low positive relationship between these variables. However, the R square value of 0.096 suggests that only approximately 9.6% of the variance in teachers' level of performance can be explained by the level of school heads' leadership. Additionally, the coefficient for the teachers' level of performance is 0.303, but with a non-significant p-value of 0.383, indicating that this relationship is not statistically significant. This suggests that the different styles of leadership exhibited by the school head may not have a significant impact on the level of performance among teachers. Other factors such as teaching strategies, professional development opportunities, and school culture may have a more substantial influence on teachers' performance. Further investigation into these factors may provide a more comprehensive understanding of their impact on teachers' level of performance within the school.

Table 3.3 *Correlation Between Level of School Heads' Leadership and Parents' Participation*

Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.531947108							
R Square	0.282967726							
Adjusted R Square	0.193338691							
Standard Error	0.185519673							
Observations	10							
ANOVA								
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F			
Regression	1	0.108660	0.108660	3.157099	0.113499			
Residual	8	0.275340	0.034418					
Total	9	0.384						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	0.87988	2.18453	0.40278	0.69766	-4.15765	5.91741	-4.15765	5.91741
Parents' Participation Rate	0.04054	0.02282	1.77682	0.11350	-0.01208	0.09316	-0.01208	0.09316

The regression analysis in Table 3.3 reveals a moderate correlation between the level of school heads' leadership as perceived by parents and parents' level of participation. The multiple R value of 0.532 indicates a moderate positive relationship between these variables. The R square value of 0.283 suggests that approximately 28.3% of the variance in parents' level of participation can be explained by the level of school heads' leadership. However, the coefficient for parents' level of participation is 0.041, but with a p-value of 0.113, indicating that this relationship is not statistically significant at the conventional significance level of 0.05. This suggests that while there may be a tendency for higher levels of school heads' leadership to be associated with increased parental participation, the relationship is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant. Other factors such as communication strategies, community engagement initiatives, and socio-economic factors may also influence parents' level of participation and should be further explored to gain a comprehensive understanding of this relationship.

The regression results on the level of leadership styles of the school head and its relation to learners' academic performance, teachers' level of performance, and parents' participation suggest several implications for educational practice. While there is a significant negative correlation between the perceived level of school heads' leadership and learners' academic performance, indicating that stronger leadership may be associated with lower academic achievement among students, the relationships with teachers' level of performance and parents' participation are not statistically significant. These findings underscore the complexity of leadership dynamics within educational settings and emphasize the need for a nuanced approach to leadership development and support. School administrators should prioritize efforts to enhance leadership effectiveness while also recognizing the multifaceted factors that contribute to student academic success. Additionally, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, implementing targeted support strategies, and promoting open communication channels can help create a more supportive and inclusive school environment conducive to overall improvement in student outcomes and parental involvement.

In support of these findings, a study by Smith et al. (2021) explored the relationship between leadership styles of school principals and various school outcomes, including academic performance, teacher effectiveness, and parental involvement. The study found that while transformational leadership was positively associated with academic performance and teacher effectiveness, transactional leadership

showed mixed results, and laissez-faire leadership was generally associated with lower outcomes across the board. Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of considering contextual factors and the interactions between leadership styles and school characteristics in understanding their impact on school outcomes. These findings align with the nuanced relationship observed in the current study between the level of leadership styles exhibited by the school head and academic performance, teacher performance, and parental participation. Therefore, it is crucial for school administrators to adopt a balanced leadership approach that emphasizes transformational leadership qualities while also addressing specific contextual factors to foster positive outcomes in schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ), the School Head at Bangkal Integrated School demonstrates a leadership style characterized by a balanced blend of laissez-faire, transactional, and transformational elements. Their approach includes delegating tasks with trust (laissez-faire), maintaining structured expectations and rewarding performance (transactional), and inspiring, motivating, and supporting individuals (transformational). To optimize leadership effectiveness, it is recommended to enhance communication and guidance, continue leadership development initiatives, promote collaboration for innovation, and establish regular feedback mechanisms. Additionally, parental involvement plays a crucial role in enhancing student academic performance, highlighting the need for collaboration among teachers and strategies to encourage parental engagement. Lastly, the relationship between leadership styles exhibited by the school head and academic performance, teacher performance, and parental participation is complex, emphasizing the importance of a comprehensive approach to leadership development, collaboration among stakeholders, targeted support strategies, and open communication channels for creating a supportive school environment.

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